

CO-OPERATIVE LEARNING AND TEAM TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

The role of teacher is becoming more and more challenging in the present scenario of education field. There is a wide scope for innovations and new practices in the process of teaching and learning. Philosophers and psychologists in the 1930s and 40's such as John Dewey, Kurt Lewin, and Morton also influenced the cooperative learning theory practiced today. David and Roger Johnson have been actively contributing to the cooperative learning theory. In 1975, they identified that cooperative learning promoted mutual liking, better communication, high acceptance and support, as well as demonstrated an increase in a variety of thinking strategies among individuals in the group. Various types of cooperative learning are formal, informal, group-based and base group learning. Brown & Ciuffetelli Parker (2009) and Siltala (2010) discussed the 5 basic and essential elements to cooperative learning. Different techniques of Cooperative Learning can be applied for the innovative practices. Team teaching can also play a vital role in effective teaching. Team teaching is an approach which involves true team work between two qualified instructors who, together, make presentations to an audience. Good preparation can prove the team teaching a better option for the fatigue in lecture method. With proper planning and efforts an individual can overcome the limitations of cooperative learning and team teaching

Introduction

Cooperative learning is an approach to organizing classroom activities into academic and social learning experiences. It differs from group work, and it has been described as "structuring positive interdependence." Students must work in groups to complete tasks collectively toward academic goals. Unlike individual learning, which can be competitive in nature, students learning cooperatively capitalize on one another's resources and skills. Furthermore, the teacher's role changes from giving information to facilitating students' learning. Five essential elements are identified for the successful incorporation of cooperative learning in the classroom.

Philosophers and psychologists in the 1930s and 40's such as John Dewey, Kurt Lewin, and Morton also influenced the cooperative learning theory practiced today. This theory portrayed students as active recipients of knowledge by discussing information and answers in groups, engaging in the learning process together rather than being passive receivers of information (e.g., teacher talking, students listening). Lewin's contributions to cooperative learning were based on the ideas of establishing relationships between group members in order to successfully carry out and achieve the learning goal.

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among individuals in the group. Students who showed to be more competitive lacked in their interaction and trust with others, as well as in their emotional involvement with other students. In 1994 Johnson and Johnson published the 5 elements positive interdependence, individual accountability, face-to-face interaction, social skills, and processing essential for effective group learning, achievement, and higher-order social, personal and cognitive skills (e.g., problem solving, reasoning, decision-making, planning, organizing, and reflecting).

Types

Formal cooperative learning is structured, facilitated, and monitored by the educator over time and is used to achieve group goals in task work (e.g. completing a unit). Any course material or assignment can be adapted to this type of learning, and groups can vary from 2-6 people with discussions lasting from a few minutes up to an entire period. Types of formal cooperative learning strategies include:

1. The jigsaw technique
2. Assignments that involve group problem solving and decision making
3. Laboratory or experiment assignments
4. Peer review work (e.g. editing writing assignments).

Having experience and developing skill with this type of learning often facilitates informal and base learning. Jigsaw activities are wonderful because the student assumes the role of the teacher on a given topic and is in charge of teaching the topic to a classmate. The idea is that if students can teach something, they have already learned the material.

Informal cooperative learning incorporates group learning with passive teaching by drawing attention to material through small groups throughout the lesson or by discussion at the end of a lesson, and typically involves groups of two (e.g. turn-to-your-partner discussions). These groups are often temporary and can change from lesson to lesson (very much unlike formal learning where 2 students may be lab partners throughout the entire semester contributing to one another's knowledge of science).

In group-based cooperative learning, the peer groups gather together over the long term (e.g. over the course of a year, or several years such as in high school or post-secondary studies) to develop and contribute to one another's knowledge mastery on a topic by regularly discussing material, encouraging one another, and supporting the academic and personal success of group members.

Base group learning (e.g., a long term study group) is effective for learning complex subject matter over the course or semester and establishes caring, supportive peer relationships, which in turn motivates and strengthens the student's commitment to the group's education while increasing self-esteem and self-worth. Base group approaches also make the students accountable to educating their peer group in the event that a member was absent for a lesson. This is effective both for individual learning, as well as social support.

Elements

Brown & Ciuffetelli Parker (2009) and Siltala (2010) discuss the 5 basic and essential elements to cooperative learning:

1. Positive interdependence
 1. Students must fully participate and put forth effort within their group
 2. Each group member has a task/role/responsibility therefore must believe that they are responsible for their learning and that of their group
2. Face-to-face promotive interaction
 1. Members promote each other's success
 2. Students explain to one another what they have or are learning and assist one another with understanding and completion of assignments
3. Individual and group accountability
 1. Each student must demonstrate mastery of the content being studied
 2. Each student is accountable for their learning and work, therefore eliminating “**social loafing**”
4. Social skills
 1. Social skills that must be taught in order for successful cooperative learning to occur
 2. Skills include effective communication, interpersonal and group skills
 1. Leadership
 2. Decision-making
 3. Trust-building
 4. Communication
 5. Conflict-management skills
5. Group processing
 1. Every so often groups must assess their effectiveness and decide how it can be improved

In order for student achievement to improve considerably, two characteristics must be present.

1. When designing cooperative learning tasks and reward structures, individual responsibility and accountability must be identified. Individuals must know exactly what their responsibilities are and that they are accountable to the group in order to reach their goal.
2. All group members must be involved in order for the group to complete the task. In order for this to occur each member must have a task that they are responsible for which cannot be completed by any other group member.

Cooperative Learning Techniques

Think Pair Share

Originally developed by Frank T. Lyman (1981) Think-Pair-Share allows for students to contemplate a posed question or problem silently. The student may write down thoughts or simply just brainstorm in his or her head. When prompted, the student pair up with a peer and discuss his or her idea(s) and then listens to the ideas of his or her partner.

Jigsaw

Students are members of two groups: home group and expert group. In the heterogeneous home group, students are each assigned a different topic. Once a topic has been identified, students leave

the home group and group with the other students with their assigned topic. In the new group, students learn the material together before returning to their home group. Once back in their home group, each student is accountable for teaching his or her assigned topic.

Jigsaw II

Jigsaw II is Robert Slavin's(1980) variation of Jigsaw in which members of the home group are assigned the same material, but focus on separate portions of the material. Each member must become an "expert" on his or her assigned portion and teach the other members of the home group.

Reverse Jigsaw

This variation was created by Timothy Hedeem (2003). It differs from the original Jigsaw during the teaching portion of the activity. In the Reverse Jigsaw technique, students in the expert groups teach the whole class rather than return to their home groups to teach the content.

Reciprocal Teaching

Brown & Paliscar (1982) developed reciprocal teaching. It is a cooperative technique that allows for student pairs to participate in a dialogue about text. Partners take turns reading and asking questions of each other, receiving immediate feedback. Such a model allows for students to use important metacognitive techniques such as clarifying, questioning, predicting, and summarizing. It embraces the idea that students can effectively learn from each other.

The Williams

Students collaborate to answer a big question that is the learning objective. Each group has differentiated questions that increase in cognitive ability to allow students to progress and meet the learning objective.

STAD (or Student-Teams-Achievement Divisions)

Students are placed in small groups or teams. The class in its entirety is presented with a lesson and the students are subsequently tested. Individuals are graded on the team's performance. Although the tests are taken individually, students are encouraged to work together to improve the overall performance of the group.

Benefits and applicability of cooperative learning:

- Students demonstrate academic achievement
- Cooperative learning methods are usually equally effective for all ability levels
- Cooperative learning is effective for all ethnic groups
- Student perceptions of one another are enhanced when given the opportunity to work with one another
- Cooperative learning increases self-esteem and self-concept
- Ethnic and physically/mentally handicapped barriers are broken down allowing for positive interactions and friendships to occur

Cooperative learning results in:

- Increased higher level reasoning
- Increased generation of new ideas and solutions
- Greater transfer of learning between situations

Cooperative learning is significant in business:

- Cooperative learning can be seen as a characteristic of innovative businesses
- The five stage division on cooperative learning creates a useful method of analyzing learning in innovative businesses
- Innovatively connected to cooperative learning seems to make the creation of innovations possible.

Limitations

- Cooperative Learning has many limitations that could cause the process to be more complicated. Due to the fact that cooperative learning is constantly changing, there is a possibility that teachers may become confused and lack complete understanding of the method.
- Teachers implementing cooperative learning may also be challenged with resistance and hostility from students who believe that they are being held back by their slower teammates or by students who are less confident and feel that they are being ignored or demeaned by their team.
- Students often provide feedback in the success of the teamwork experienced during cooperative learning experiences. Peer review and evaluations may not reflect true experiences due to perceived competition among peers. A confidential evaluation process may help to increase evaluation strength.

Team Teaching

In team teaching a group of teachers, working together, plan, conduct, and evaluate the learning activities for the same group of students. It is a means of organizing staff into groups to enhance teaching. To facilitate this process a common teaching space is desirable. However, to be effective team teaching requires much more than just a common meeting time and space.

"Team Teaching is an Alternative to Lecture Fatigue"

Team teaching is an approach which involves true team work between two qualified instructors who, together, make presentations to an audience. The instructional advantages of team teaching include:

- 1) Lecture-style instruction is eliminated in favor of a dynamic interplay of two minds and personalities.
- 2) Teaching staff act as role models for discussion and disagreement.
- 3) Team teaching makes effective use of existing human resources.
- 4) Team teaching has the potential for revitalizing instructional capabilities through a process of dialogue.
- 5) Interest in traditional courses can be stimulated as students share the enthusiasm and intellectual discourse that the lecturers communicate.
- 6) The effective use of facilities is possible.
- 7) Team teaching provides opportunities for interaction with the audience.

Its format needs to be adapted to the requirements of the teaching situation. Some possible options are as follows:

- Two or more teachers teach the same group at the same time;

- Team members meet to share ideas and resources but generally function independently;
- Teams of teachers share a common resource center;
- A team shares a common group of students, shares planning for instruction but team members teach different sub-groups within the whole group;
- Planning is shared, but teachers teach their own skills area to the whole group;
- Teams plan and develop teaching resource materials for a large group of students but may or may not teach them in a classroom situation

Limitations:

- Not all team members will contribute equally;
- Teachers do not understand how to make the team work;
- There will be personality conflicts to deal with in addition to the teaching itself;
- A preference for working alone; all the work will fall on the team leader/senior subject expert;
- It will be too difficult to cover all the course content;
 - Team meetings will be a waste of time.

Planning for Teaching

This short list of questions underlines the decisions to be made in this area.

- What are the program, unit, and lesson objectives?
- What lesson content is to be presented and in what order?
- Which content is to be presented by large group presentation?
- Which methods and resources are to be used to present the content?
- Who will make large group presentations?
- What will be discussed during small group meetings?
- How will small groups be organized?
- Who will be assigned to each small group?
- What types of independent study will be appropriate?
- What blocks of time will be assigned to large-group, small group and independent study activities?
- How will students be assessed?

Conclusion

- Teams take a variety of forms in different contexts; however, successful team teaching must go beyond sharing a group of students and scheduling a common meeting time if it is to make positive contributions to the quality of learning and staff development.
- Effective team teaching takes time to develop to its fullest potential. Staff who are unfamiliar with it need time to work through the basic issues and routine matters before they can turn their attention fully to issues which affect students and to the impact which their teaching has on the department as a whole. This is time well spent because team teaching can be a valuable source of personal and professional development for those who engage in it. It can also be a source of considerable frustration if its goals are unrealistic, meetings are not productive and decision making is not well handled by team leaders.

- These pitfalls and others can be avoided or at least not encountered more than once if adequate staff development support is available and the relative complexity of demands which team teaching places on people is recognized both by the individuals themselves and their departmental leaders.

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